

Smart Switching Home Automated Control System Using Android Application and Microcontroller

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ABSTRACT – As time goes on, technology advances worldwide, and humanity will soon be centred around technology. Thus, in order to create the cutting-edge next generation of technologies, people need to do some basic steps. Accordingly, an Android application utilizing an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, relay, logic level converter module, and Wi-Fi technology to operate switches has been developed as part of the proposed study work.

Keywords – Smart switch, IoT, Wi-Fi technology, Android application.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of a smartphone or other smart device, customers may now remotely manage electrical appliances thanks to the novel IoT-based Smart Switch. The design, use, and implementation of the Smart Switch are all covered in detail in this documentation. The Internet of Things or IoT, is essential in today's technologically advanced world. Everything connected to the internet will undergo fresh development as the internet of things grows. Internet, WIFI, and Bluetooth are some of the new connections brought about by the advancement of wireless technology [1]. Additionally, smart switch systems have made an effort to give residents especially the elderly population an effective, practical, appropriate, and safe means to enter their homes. The idea of security in contemporary dwellings will be introduced.

Time is essential for finishing all of the duties that are given to humans, and it is human nature to anticipate that scheduled chores will be finished within the allocated time. Automation technologies are necessary when there are duties that need to be completed at home without their presence. To do this, you can use any location in the world to access the web and use it to control and monitor your home's electronics-based devices [2]. Along with the automated house temperature, light force detector, fire initiation, LPG gas spill detection, water level marker, automatic fan speed, and the option to install automatic windows and entryway close and open, the suggested model IOT-based automation framework has been put into place.

Modern culture, which is intrinsically tied to innovation, is interested in developing the most intelligent frameworks. Human lives have been easier and more convenient thanks to technology. Integrating the environment and people with the latest technology could be crucial in creating a new framework that continuously influences how people live their lives. The world is moving toward innovation because without it, nobody can operate as they should. Recent technological advancements are also essential to our daily lives because they make us feel more at ease.

Two methods have been used to design and operate a smart switch in the proposed IoT-based smart switch control system [SSCS]. By linking modern homes to the Internet, consumers may now access and control their homes remotely at any time and from any location [3]. The rise in processing power of newly-designed processors is primarily responsible for the reduction in power consumption, price, and capacity of modern electronics products.

First of all, by moving to a different location, any device that has been connected to Wi-Fi can turn on or off. Second, a smart switch can be operated manually in the event that Wi-Fi is unavailable. IoT devices can be used to monitor and manage industrial automation systems as well as mechanical, electrical, and electronic

systems that are utilized in a variety of settings, such as public and private, industrial, institutional, or domestic [4].

1.1. IOT BASED SMART SWITCH

IoT refers to a global network of interconnected and immeasurable things. An advanced IoT network is being created as the public wants to connect to different things. The term IoT is used for the development of smart homes to improve living conditions [5]. It provides a vision for the integration of services, tools and systems. It uniquely represents not only the computer system but also the current Internet architecture [6]. It offers us powerful tools in the field of communication and information. There are three main entities in the IoT ecosystem: consumer, government, and business objectives [7]. The IoT network acts as a bridge between devices and the data network. IoT security and privacy have become a major concern among consumers and businesses [8].

a) Some advantages of IoT:

- The best way.
- Save time.
- Price reduction.
- Control and operation of all kinds of systems.
- Independent ad-hoc monitoring and feedback for complex tasks.
- Real-time system calculation.
- Reduce data collection errors.
- Develop character.
- Start the operating system.
- Reduce costs and energy consumption.

It is easy to communicate with things in our daily lives. A single or standard computer is used at home to manage basic household tasks consciously and sometimes remotely [9]. An automated home is also called a smart home. To connect residential objects via the Internet, we need a platform known as the Internet of Things (IoT) [10]. We use IoT because it provides an environment where we can easily integrate the internet and remote servers or any wireless devices such as laptops, internet, Wi-Fi, mobile phones and tabs.

1.2. BACKGROUND OF SMART SWITCHING IDEA

Changing your mind was an idea, not a real process. Although furniture in the early twentieth century (1901-1920) was not considered smart. The first electric motor machine was invented in 1901, and the vacuum cleaner was invented in 1907. Although ECHO 4 was the first smart machine, it did not enter the market until 1966-1967. In 1990, this homeschool department embarked on new research and development. By the early 21st century the exchange of information had become exoteric and various terms began to appear. Like many other fields, the IoT field is developing rapidly. However, this development brings with it many problems regarding internet security. Fundamental research in the field of IoT has mainly focused on finding control strategies to solve problems in various areas of IoT, including security, privacy, vulnerability, and resilience [12] – [15]. However, the need for security principles and evaluation methods specifically targeting IoT environments based on technology is as important as the research itself. As a background to current research work, this chapter will focus on security and privacy issues. addresses the environment based on existing research on IoT intelligence and security measures or evaluation criteria [16]. We can now control the electricity at home [17].

2. PROPOSED SYSTEM FRAMEWORK

(A) Features of the system:

The quick transition from traditional analog norms to an easy-to-improvise method to achieve the identical results in the twenty-first century will make life simpler and easier [18, 19]. The famous see-saw switches will no longer just replace the clicking switches with touch activation—a single touch toggles the switch between ON and OFF—thanks to the addition of touch sensors and an elegant, immersive design. In addition to touch activation, cell phones are utilized for controlling triggering operations and reducing time/effort spent in other ways, all while facilitating communication. Numerous attempts have been made to simplify and modify the conventional approaches and knowledge of how to activate a switch. The electronics in use now facilitates easier.

(B) Proposed system working:

The switches can be turned on and off with the help of the end user's fingertips because they are touch-sensitive. Alternatively, mobile phones can be used to achieve the same result by simply using the application, which adds another level of convenience for controlling the same device from anywhere in the world. The device being used for control will be checked to verify if it is authorized to do so before any initial verification takes place when a user wants to engage the control switches. Subsequently, the information will be displayed through an app, and a single tap will be sufficient to toggle the current condition. Additionally, the app will show the switches.

Block diagram:

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed system [20]

3. ANALYSIS OF PROPOSED SYSTEM FRAMEWORK

(A) Working Principle:

Relay and TTP223 touch sensor require 5 volts of DC power supply to function. Therefore, a Hi-link 5v power supply with a function to convert 230v AC to 5v DC is used for power. In offline mode, TTP223 is used to control the device and socket. To give it a more contemporary appearance, the suggested project has swapped out the old switches for a TTP223 touch sensor. The configuration terminal B of the TTP223 has been soldered in order to control the device or socket. The sensor will start to function if you do this. The gadget is turned on when the user touches the sensor, which transmits a signal to the relay module. If the sensor is touched again, the same procedure will occur. The ESP8266-01 Wi-Fi module is used to control the device or socket in online mode. ESP8266-01 is managed by the application that has been developed. 3.3V is the voltage at which the ESP8266-01 operates. To convert 5 volts DC to 3.3 volts DC, a voltage regulator, AMS1117 H, is needed.

Figure 2: Flow chart of System Design [21]

A few hardware and software tools have also been employed in the proposed project work. These are:

(a) Hardware tools:

I. ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module

Figure 3: ESP8266 Wi-Fi module

ESP8266 is a fully standalone Wi-Fi network solution with a separate application processor that allows it to disable all Wi-Fi networking features or control software applications. Even if the ESP8266 device is ascending and is thought to be the only application for the processor, the flash memory can be started straight from an external source. Cache memory that is built into the system will aid to reduce memory usage and enhance system performance. The second scenario is a wireless adapter that may be connected to any microcontroller-based design via an SPI/SDIO interface or a central processor with an AHB bridge interface. This type of connection is simple to make. GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) [22] ports and other application-specific devices can be used to combine the processing and storage capability of the powerful ESP8266 device. With its antenna switch, power management converter, minimal extra circuitry, and front-end module, the ESP8266 is a highly nonsegregated chip that incorporates the entire solution design to minimize PCB area. The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi chip with full TCP/IP stack and microcontroller capability produced by Shanghai-based Chinese manufacturer, Espressif [23]. Below are the names and functions of the pins:

Table: Pin configuration of ESP8266 Wi-Fi module [24]

Pin No.	Pin Name	Description
1	VCC	Power supply (3.3V)
2	GPIO2	General-purpose I/O
3	GPIO0	General-purpose I/O
4	GND	Ground
5	GPIO3	General-purpose I/O
6	URXD	UART Receive (Serial)
7	UTXD	UART Transmit (Serial)

PIN Configuration [25, 26]

The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module has the following features:

- It is an integrated, low-power 32-bit microcontroller unit.
- An integrated 10-bit ADC is present.
- The TCP/IP protocol stack is also built into the ESP8266.
- Has integrated power management units, regulators, and PLL.
- Accommodates nearly every kind of antenna; o Facilitates 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi, WPA / WPA2;
- Accommodates STA / AP / STA + AP modes of operation;
- Facilitates the Smart Link feature for Android and iOS devices. [24]

II. 4 channel Relay module (5v)

Figure 4: 4 channel Relay module (5v)

There are relay modules available to regulate external loads. Relays employ steel transfer contacts instead of transistors, which prevents the heating and strength loss that come with using transistors in switching circuits. They come with small modules that are ideal for AC switching and are simple to connect. Relays' primary disadvantage is that, like all mechanical transfer relays, they are an electro-mechanical device, making them particularly prone to wear and tear over time. These relays are totally suitable with 5V devices [27]. The device can be powered with less than five mA at the superb judgement control pin of the instrument since the inputs have an integrated relay driving force transistor and opto-isolator. Any of the virtual output pins on an Arduino can be used to power the relays. Relays are turned on by a low signal that requires good judgment. The manage pin for that relay is pushed low to turn the relay off, and the purple LED is turned ON. There may be an audible click when the relay is turned on. The LED will turn off when the relay is turned off with a high decision. Opto-isolators at the good judgment inputs make up the board. As a guaranteed layer of protection in the event of a lighting fixture strike or several other sorts of primary failure at the AC loads of the relay, opto-isolators provide complete electric isolation between the excellent judgment to control enters and the relay strength. A jumper between header pins, such as JD-VCC and VCC, is present in the module as shipped (relay strength is jumper to good judgment strength). Because it connects the relay strength to the excellent judgment strength, this avoids the opto-isolation circuit. The instrument is made easy to use by a single strength that full fills its desire to be connected to the module.

In the event that opto-isolation is required, the jumper has been removed to deliver a different 5V supply voltage to the JD-VCC and GND pins on that connection. For the module to function, 5V power and GND are required. If opt isolation is used, certain 5V strength sources are needed. With the uC, the floor must be in an odd location. Flyback diodes are connected in parallel to the relay coils at the module to provide a contemporary, sound-shunting effect while the relay coil is de-energized. A relay that is activated draws about 70mA from the VCC pin of the module. After all relays are turned on, the 140mA draw is prepared. As per the relay markings, the output of the relay can switch up to 30VDC at 10A or up to 125/250VAC at up to 10A. With a NO (Normally Open) and an NC (Normally Closed) [26] terminal connected to the middle unmarked uncommon place (COM) terminal; the output is SPDT in type. A sound judgment the NO-COM

touch is closed and the NC-COM touch is open when HIGH energizes the relay. The relay is de-energized by a prudent low voltage, leaving the NO-COM touch open and the NC-COM touch closed.

A 4-volt channel relay module can do the following:

- Its digital output is controlled.
- The relay module works with any 5V microcontroller, including Arduino.
- Through-current rating: 5A (NC) and 10A (NO).
- Signal control: TTL level
- 250VAC/30VDC maximum switching voltage
- A relay module's maximum switching current is 10A [24].

(b) Software tools:

- Blynk App Inventor

Blynk [28] is an Internet-based platform of free programs for iOS and Android that manages Arduino, Raspberry Pi, and other devices. Blynk is an Internet of Things device that may be used to take images, save data, show sensor data, control hardware remotely, and carry out several other useful functions. The Blynk App, Blynk Server, and Blynk Library are the three primary parts of the platform [29].

Figure 5: App

Figure 6: Switch OFF

Figure 7: Switch ON

4. RESULT

With the help of an Android smartphone and smart switch, this paper has effectively developed a Wi-Fi-based automation system for smart home and industrial automation.

The Android phone first establishes a connection to the Internet or a nearby Wi-Fi module. Any mobile phone can open the produced applications, but before connecting to the device, a username and password need to be created. In the command prompt, you may find the username and password. Additionally, since all electrical appliances are now controllable, it is possible to monitor the house's humidity, temperature, and motion.

The web server receives the sensor data after a successful connection to the server, which allows for system monitoring. We will be able to monitor and manage the system thanks to the web server. The main

page will show up after the allotted user ID and password are entered on the server page. The web server provides details about the room's motion status and various locations' temperatures. It also provides the status of other electrical equipment, such as fans, lights, and others, that may be operated with a physical switch or a mobile application.

Figure 8: Switch OFF

Figure 9: Switch ON

5. CONCLUSION

Using an Android smart phone and an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, the suggested research study has designed and built a prototype of an affordable Wi-Fi based automation system for smart home and industrial usage. The automation system for smart switches will offer a safe and intelligent solution to improve people's quality of life. Several sensors have been developed by this research project to improve security and safety in addition to completely automated appliances.

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